

MECHANISMS FOR PROVIDING PSYCHOLOGICAL SERVICES TO SMALL GROUPS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *The article states that the psychological service of groups today is effectively treated as a socio-psychological problem. In Uzbekistan, as in all developed countries, it is important to study, analyze and comprehend how and on what scientific and organizational basis this problem of psychological service is being solved.*

Key words: *self-awareness, small group, formal group, informal group, group activity, group attitude, motive, attitude.*

МЕХАНИЗМЫ ОКАЗАНИЯ ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ УСЛУГ МАЛЫМ ГРУППАМ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

Аннотация. *В статье констатируется, что психологическое обслуживание групп сегодня эффективно практикуется как социально-психологическая проблема. В Узбекистане, как и во всех развитых странах, важно изучить, проанализировать и осмыслить, как и на какой научной и организационной основе решается эта проблема психологической службы. **Ключевые слова:** самосознание, малая группа, формальная группа, неформальная группа, групповая активность, групповая установка, мотив, установка.*

The Uzbek people and representatives of other nationalities living in Uzbekistan have a culture of behavior, morals and values that have been formed and improved over the centuries and are highly valued in world civilization. However, there are some aspects of these noble human relationships that create specific features in the organization and conduct of socio-psychological training. For example, following the opinions of others, taking into account one's age and life experience, reputation in society under any circumstances, the qualities of a person's memory when criticizing or self-criticism, openly expressing one's emotional experiences in front of others - without making a clear statement - can interfere with the organization and conduct of socio-psychological training in European standards. Secondly, if we take into account the desire of people, especially young people, for news, new innovative technologies, the desire to study foreign languages and the talent of young people in this regard, then a logical question arises whether it is advisable to organize for them training at the level of world requirements only for youth audience.

It is impossible to comment on the issue of further improvement and development of psychological services in Uzbekistan without a proper assessment of the scale of theoretical, scientific and practical methodological research conducted in the republic. In addition, when preparing children for school, when improving educational tasks, when determining specific individual psychological characteristics and interests of students, when orienting them to a particular profession, in their self-awareness, the educational process, there is sufficient evidence of today's achievements of psychologists-scientists in finding ways to eliminate all problems associated with the student community and student teaching activities. For example, I.V. Justification of theoretical and practical aspects of organizing psychological services in schools in the study of Dubrovina, L.I. Boyovich's empirical data on the psychological

classification of a student's personality and the stages of its formation at school age, A.G. Asmolov's research explaining student activity and attitudinal harmony, D.I. A series of scientific and practical instructions by Feldstein aimed at revealing the psychological patterns of human social development that develop in ontogenesis, E.A. Klimov's development of psychological criteria, including the individual style of student orientation towards the profession, B.S. Merlin's works were aimed at explaining the psychology of individual and social typical personality traits of a student, E.G. Gaziev's instructions for recording the tasks of psychological services in educational institutions, M.G. Scientific and practical views of Davletshin, aimed at interpreting the current situation and tasks of psychological services in Uzbekistan, V.A. Tokareva's scientific and empirical data are aimed at revealing the possibilities of self-knowledge and moral development, important for the development of a student's personality, G'.B. Shumarov's theoretical, scientific and socio-practical views on innovations, problems and ways to solve them related to the introduction of psychological services into the public education system, B.R. Among them are a number of scientific, theoretical and practical methodological works by Kadirov aimed at selecting and training gifted and talented children in Uzbekistan.

Especially today, by a group of Uzbek psychologists and the Ministry, the approval of public education is of great social importance for the official "revival" and development of the psychological service system in Uzbekistan. Naturally, this "Regulation" is the original goal, content, essence, meaning, objectives and main functions of the psychological service. System for implementation in educational institutions, it serves as a unique guide and guide to create a sufficient idea of the directions and work successfully on the basis of this idea.

Thus, the above scientific observations, which serve as a methodological basis for providing psychological assistance to small groups, require us to consider the following areas of modern social psychology as a practical problem requiring immediate solution.

1. The practical tasks of social psychology can be determined by considering formal and informal subgroups operating in secondary schools within the framework of psychological services as a separate object of research and empirically assessing the scope of its unique group, regional and ethno psychological capabilities.

2. Creation of a methodology for providing psychological assistance to small groups based on scientific developments studying a person and his social activities; It can be noted that it is directly related to empirical data directly examining group identification and group social institutions, scientific explanations related to the study of interpersonal activity and motivations for interpersonal relationships in a group.

3. The use of well-known and popular tests in the scientific press, including the results of eight octants aimed at studying interpersonal motivation in small groups based on the Leary test, as well as five situations based on the results of the Thomas test. (dispute, cooperation, mutual agreement, leaving the group, adaptation to the group) is studied based on the requirements of group psychology, the study of small groups in all aspects and the provision of psychological services to them.

4. The creation of studies related to self-emotional assessment in the study of small groups provides them with direct psychological assistance.

5. An important methodological source is the study of criteria in a group, a system of socio-psychological relief associated with the composition of a student's personality and the motivation of interpersonal activities within small groups, developed by the famous psychologist R.S. Nemov. in determining the effectiveness of psychological services today.

It is known that the process of psychological assistance carried out in secondary schools has a wide range of directions and each direction has its own goals and objectives. These tasks must be performed by practicing psychologists with special knowledge and experience. Moreover, the high prospects of educational institutions in all developed countries today cannot be imagined without the practice of psychological services organized on the basis of specific social goals. Because the student is the object and subject of any education. The student's personality is a conscious social being, formed on the basis of certain social influences and possessing many unique psychological capabilities. Therefore, it is worth saying that if we want to achieve the effectiveness of education, and also if we want to prepare a well-rounded, well-rounded personality necessary for the development of society, psychological aspects should be taken into account first. Capabilities of this person and the direct positive or negative impact on him, it is inevitable that we empirically study and analyze mysterious socio-psychological factors and carry out educational work based on these analyzes. From this point of view, it is necessary to empirically study the subgroups that today directly influence the socialization of each schoolchild, and interpret each studied factor based on the requirements of the psychological service, and based on these interpretations, practicing school psychologists develop specific recommendations.

Providing psychological assistance to small groups at school is directly related to the formation of interpersonal motivation within these small groups. Because it is very difficult to direct the activities of these groups in a positive direction if the school psychologist does not analyze the manifestations of interpersonal motivation from a social point of view. From this point of view, it is necessary to determine the main directions of providing psychological services to small groups through a comparative analysis of the formal and informal layers in each group.

The methodological basis showed that the interpretation of the personality of each student, his socio-psychological nature, capabilities and unique psychological perspectives within the small groups in which he is active, and based on these interpretations of psychological services of a certain level for him, demonstration is one of the important tasks facing with educational institutions. Consequently, the educational reforms being carried out today in our republic with a unique sequence, socio-economic relations rising to a higher level, the interaction of society and individual needs capable of responding to the dramatic development of science, technology and the extremely important issue of determining the directions of research aimed at studying processes of group activity, formed on the basis of certain psychological criteria

REFERENCES

1. Andreeva G.M. Textbook of social psychology for high school. - M.: Aspect-Press, 2001-378s.)
2. Ageev V.S. Relational psychology. M., 1983.
3. Barotov Sh.R. Fundamentals of psychological services in education. Monograph. T. Spirituality. 1999.

4. Barotov Sh.R. Psychological service.-T.: Publishing house “Navruz”, 2018. B.-344.
5. Nishonova Z.T. and head Psychological service. – T.: Publishing House of the Scientific and Technical Center, 2014.
6. Khudoikulova G.B. Social and psychological mechanisms of teaching student groups. Psychology No. 4. 2016 B 78 -81.
7. Khudoikulova G.B. Scientific and practical principles of providing psychological assistance to groups of students at school Monograph. Tashkent “Fan” 2013. 143 pp..
8. Nurqulova, G., & Saydaliyeva, M. (2023). PSYCHOLOGICAL METHODS OF EDUCATION AND DEVELOPMENT ACCORDING TO THE CHILD'S TEMPERAMENT. *International Bulletin of Engineering and Technology*, 3(10), 92-95.
9. Muhiddinova, D., & Saydaliyeva, M. (2023). MANIFESTATION OF DESTRUCTIVE RELIGIOUS BEHAVIOR IN PERSONAL CHARACTERISTICS. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(6), 934-938.